

A Generalised Equation for the Determination of Hydration Number of Ions[†]

M. L. SOOD

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

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A new generalised equation for the determination of hydration number of ions has been theoretically obtained. This equation can be successfully used for the determination of hydration number not only in the primary and secondary hydration spheres but in a sphere of any order. The equation, however, failed to predict the sign of the hydration number.

THE phenomenon of hydration is still in the developing stage and no exact explanation is available so far. Due to the process of hydration, the solution must contain ions with a solvent sheath rather than free ions. Bockris¹ and Bockris and Conway² have distinguished between the primary and the secondary solvent sheath (or shell). The former include solvent molecules strongly bound with an ion and moving together with it, and the latter all the molecules the state of which is different from that of water molecules in a pure solvent. It is very important for many electrochemical processes to know how many solvent molecules are inside the primary sheath and this number is generally known as solvation number or hydration number when water is the solvent. These are

relative values which provide only approximate information about the hydration number contained in the primary or internal shell. Somoilov³ later developed the concept of hydration on the basis of the translational motion of the solvent molecules closest to the ion in the solution. These authors however failed to provide any theoretical approach for the determination of hydration number and further all the existing methods that yield hydration number give widely differing hydration values. This is clear from the data recorded in Table 1. This variation in hydration number may be considered to be due to the fact that the value which a particular method gives depends on what types of ion-solvent interactions it senses. A survey of literature clearly indicates that presently there exists no experimental or theoretical method by which the exact number of water molecules in the primary or in the secondary shell can be obtained separately. Based on this idea, simple theoretical equations were recently developed by the author⁴ and primary and secondary hydration numbers were obtained for few ions. In this communication, these equations are now been generalised and hydration numbers in the primary as well as in the secondary shell determined for a large number of ions.

Results and Discussion

Let us consider any ion with radius r_{ion} , surrounded by a number of water molecules forming the primary hydration sphere. These water molecules will be oriented in such a manner that there will be a firm binding in addition to the 'free' motion of the ion. The term 'free' simply means that the ion with the primary hydration sphere moves as a single kinetic entity in a solution. For secondary hydration sphere, however, there will be variation in the number of water molecules since these are considered to be loosely bound to the central ion. It is also assumed that the water molecules around an ion form a sphere of oriented water

TABLE 1—HYDRATION NUMBERS OBTAINED FROM DIFFERENT METHODS

Salt	From compressibility ^a	Hydration numbers			
		From activity ^a	From diffusion ^a	Due to Stokes and Robin-son ^b	Due to Sugden ^c
LiCl	6	7.1	6.3	7.1	10.5
LiBr	5-6	7.6	5.6	7.6	9.0
LiI	-	-	-	9.0	-
NaCl	7	3.5	3.5	3.5	7.9
NaBr	6-7	4.2	2.8	4.2	6.4
NaI	6-7	5.5	3.0	5.5	-
KCl	7	1.9	0.6	1.9	3.4
KBr	6-7	2.1	0.3	2.1	1.9
KF, NaF	8-9	17.0	-	-	-
RbCl	-	-	-	1.2	-
RbBr	-	-	-	0.9	-
RbI	-	-	-	0.6	-
CaCl ₂	-	-	-	12.0	-
CaBr ₂	-	-	-	14.6	-
CaI ₂	-	-	-	17.0	-
MgCl ₂	16-17	13.1	-	13.7	-
MgBr ₂	-	-	-	17.0	-
MgI ₂	-	-	-	19.0	-
MnCl ₂	-	-	-	11.0	-

^aRef. 7. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 8.

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molecules but with radius nearly equal to the sum of the radius of the ion plus that of the water molecule. The properties of the water molecules in spheres other than the primary and secondary ones are also assumed to be that of 'bulk water' similar to the views expressed by earlier workers¹⁻³.

Based on the above fact we can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Radius of primary hydration sphere} &= r_{\text{ion}} + r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \\ &= r_{\text{primary}} \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Radius of secondary hydration sphere} &= r_{\text{primary}} \\ &\quad + r_{\text{ion}} \\ &= r_{\text{secondary}} \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Once the radius of the primary and secondary hydration spheres have been calculated, the maximum number of water molecules can be determined from the area of the sphere and that occupied by water molecules around this sphere. Further, since hydration depends upon the charge density of the ion which in turn is inversely proportional to the ionic radius, we can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hydration number in any sphere} \\ = \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(\frac{\text{Area of hydration sphere}}{\text{Area of water molecules}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Now, the area of the primary and secondary hydration spheres are $4\pi r_{\text{primary}}^2$ and $4\pi r_{\text{secondary}}^2$ and that of the sphere containing water molecules would be $4\pi r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2$, respectively. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Primary hydration number} &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(\frac{4\pi r_{\text{primary}}^2}{4\pi r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2} \right) \quad (3) \\ &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}} + r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \right)^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(1 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \right)^2 \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

Secondary hydration number

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(\frac{4\pi r_{\text{secondary}}^2}{4\pi r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2} \right) = \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(\frac{r_{\text{secondary}}^2}{r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(\frac{r_{\text{primary}} + r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \right)^2 \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Secondary hydration number} = \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(2 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

For higher order one can obtain,

$$\text{Tertiary hydration number} = \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(3 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Quaternary hydration number} = \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(4 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

and so on. In these equations, r_{ion} is the radius of the ion and r_{water} is that of water molecule.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hydration number (nth order)} &= (\text{Primary hydration number} + \text{secondary hydration number} + \text{tertiary hydration number} + \text{quaternary hydration number} + \dots) \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting from equations (4), (6), (7), (8) ... in equation (6),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hydration number (total)} &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(1 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(2 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(3 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left(4 + \frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + \dots \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

On solving this one gets,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hydration number (total)} &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left[1 + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \right. \\ &+ 2 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + 4 + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + 4 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + 9 + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \\ &+ 6 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + 16 + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + 8 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + \dots \left. \right] \quad (11) \\ &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left[(1+4+9+16+\dots) + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \right. \\ &+ \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + \dots + 2 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) \\ &+ 4 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + 6 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + 8 \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) + \dots \left. \right] \quad (12) \\ &= \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left[(1+4+9+16+\dots) + (1+1+1+\dots) \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 \right. \\ &+ \left. \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) (2+4+6+8+\dots) \right] \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

In general,

$$\text{Hydration number (nth order)} = \frac{1}{r_{\text{ion}}} \left[n^2 + \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right)^2 + 2n \left(\frac{r_{\text{ion}}}{r_{\text{water}}} \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

where, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$ for primary hydration number ($n=1$), secondary hydration number ($n=2$), tertiary hydration number ($n=3$) etc. Equation (14) is a generalised one since hydration number in any sphere around a particular ion can be determined with this provided the radius of the ion and that of the water molecule are known. The above equation has been tested for a large number of ions and hydration number calculated in primary and secondary hydration spheres. The sum of primary and secondary hydration number are also calculated and these are recorded in

TABLE 2—PRIMARY AND SECONDARY HYDRATION NUMBERS (RADIUS OF WATER MOLECULE TAKEN AS 1.40 Å)

Ion*	Ionic radii	Hydration number		Total hydration (Primary+Secondary)
		Primary	Secondary	
Li ⁺	0.60	3.40	9.83	13.23
Na ⁺	0.95	2.96	7.55	10.51
K ⁺	1.33	2.86	6.54	9.40
Rb ⁺	1.48	2.86	6.31	9.17
Cs ⁺	1.69	2.88	6.09	8.97
Ca ²⁺	0.99	2.94	7.40	10.34
Mg ²⁺	0.65	3.30	9.34	11.64
Mn ²⁺	0.80	3.09	8.27	11.36
Cu ⁺	0.96	2.96	7.51	10.47
Ag ⁺	1.26	2.86	6.67	9.54
Au ⁺	1.37	2.85	6.47	9.33
Be ²⁺	0.31	4.81	15.91	20.73
Zn ²⁺	0.74	3.15	8.64	11.79
Sr ²⁺	1.13	2.89	6.97	9.86
Cd ²⁺	0.97	2.95	7.47	10.42
Ba ²⁺	1.35	2.85	2.50	9.36
Hg ²⁺	1.35	2.89	7.05	9.95
Al ³⁺	0.50	3.68	11.11	14.79
Sn ⁴⁺	0.71	3.19	8.85	12.05
Si ⁴⁺	0.41	4.07	12.82	16.89
Mn ⁷⁺	0.46	3.83	11.78	15.62
F ⁻	1.36	2.86	6.49	9.35
Cl ⁻	1.81	2.90	5.99	8.89
Br ⁻	1.95	2.93	5.90	8.83
I ⁻	2.16	2.99	5.81	8.80
La ³⁺	1.15	2.88	6.92	9.80
Tl ³⁺	0.95	2.96	7.75	10.51
Zr ⁴⁺	0.80	3.08	8.27	11.35
Ce ⁴⁺	1.01	2.93	7.73	10.26
Pb ⁴⁺	0.84	3.05	8.05	11.10
V ⁵⁺	0.59	3.42	9.94	13.36
Sb ⁵⁺	0.62	3.36	9.63	12.99
Bi ⁵⁺	0.74	3.16	8.64	11.80
Cr ⁶⁺	0.52	3.62	10.81	14.43
Mo ⁶⁺	0.62	3.36	9.62	12.98

*Anions such as F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ are hydrated and literature (Ref. 9) values reported are 2, 1, 0, 0 and 4, 2, 1.8 and 1.5 respectively (Ref. 10).

Table 2. Comparison of these are made with the available values obtained from experimental methods (Table 1) and it is clear that the agreement is satisfactory. However, it is worth mentioning here that out of the available methods for determining hydration number, those based on the transport of the ion through the solvent may be considered to be more reliable as compared to others. This is due to the fact that in such methods, the interactions pickup will probably be those of the ion with the firmly bound water molecules (primary hydration number) alone and the influence of water molecules in the secondary hydration sphere will be very less although it can not be taken equal to zero. Therefore, on this basis an assessment of the various methods will clearly indicate that the hydration numbers as recorded in Table 1 from diffusion experiments might provide reliable data as compared to other methods. The equation (10) does not give any idea about the sign of the hydration number. The sign is important since negative values of hydration number have also been reported in literature⁴⁻⁶. Some workers have suggested that negative hydration is due to depolymerisation, but so far no clear picture about this is available and no physical meaning can now be attached to it. The equation developed above is useful in the sense that hydration number of all the ions can be easily determined although experimental data are not available for obtaining it.

The theory of electrolytic solution may be further developed by incorporating the fact that the ions exist as hydrated species and not as bare ions and for which sufficient data are available in literature and need no further description.

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References

1. J. O' M. BOCKRIS, *Quart. Rev.*, 1949, 3, 173.
2. J. O' M. BOCKRIS and B. E. REDDY, "Modern Electrochemistry", Plenum, New York, 1970, Vols. 1, 2.
3. O. YA, SAMOILOV, "Structure and Hydration of Ions", Consultant Bureau, New York, 1965.
4. M. L. SOOD, *J. Res.*, 1979, 14, 320.
5. R. H. STOKES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1870.
6. M. L. SOOD and G. KAUR, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, 259, 585.
7. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", 2nd. ed., 1970, pp. 54, 461.
8. J. N. SUGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 174.
9. A. PASSYNSKI, *Acta Phys. Chim.*, 1938, 8, 385.
10. J. O' M. BOCKRIS and P. P. S. SALUJA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, 76, 2140.